

1 *Spiribacter curvatus* sp. nov., a new moderately halophilic bacterium from Santa Pola
2 saltern in Spain

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20 The GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ accession number for the 16S rRNA gene sequence of
21 strain UAH-SP71^T is available from the complete genome sequence deposited as
22 CP005990.

23 A novel pink-pigmented bacterial strain, UAH-SP71^T, was isolated from a saltern
24 located in Santa Pola, Alicante (Spain) and the complete genome sequence was
25 analysed and compared with that of *Spiribacter salinus*, suggesting that they
26 constituted two separate species, with a 77.3 % ANI value. In this paper this strain
27 was investigated by a polyphasic taxonomic approach. It was a Gram-staining-
28 negative, strictly aerobic, non-motile curved rod that grew in media containing 5-
29 20% (w/v) NaCl (optimally at 10% [w/v] NaCl), at 5-40 °C (optimally at 37 °C) and
30 at pH 5-10 (optimally at pH 8). Phylogenetic analysis based on the comparison of
31 16S rRNA gene sequences revealed that strain UAH-SP71^T is a member of the
32 genus *Spiribacter*, showing a sequence similarity of 96.5 % with *Spiribacter salinus*
33 M19-40^T. Other related species are also members of the family
34 *Ectothiorhodospiraceae*: *Arhodomonas recens* RS91^T (95.5 % sequence similarity),
35 *Arhodomonas aquaeolei* ATCC 49307^T (95.4 %) and *Alkalilimnicola ehrlichii*
36 MLHE-1^T (94.9 %). DNA-DNA hybridization between strain UAH-SP71^T and
37 *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T was 39 %. The major cellular fatty acids of strain
38 UAH-SP71^T were C_{18:1} ω_{6c} and/or C_{18:1} ω_{7c}, C_{16:0}, C_{16:1} ω_{6c} and/or C_{16:1} ω_{7c}, C_{10:0}
39 3-OH and C_{12:0}, a pattern similar to that of *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T.
40 Phylogenetic, phenotypic and genotypic differences between strain UAH-SP71^T
41 and *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T indicate that this strain represents a novel species
42 in the genus *Spiribacter* for which the name *Spiribacter curvatus* sp. nov. is
43 proposed, with the type strain UAH-SP71^T (= CECT 8396^T = DSM 28542^T).

44

45 Metagenomic studies on marine salterns located in Spain have permitted to determine in
46 detail the prokaryotic diversity of these hypersaline habitats, and complemented early
47 studies on these extreme environments based on traditional and molecular
48 methodologies (Ghai *et al.*, 2011; Fernández *et al.*, 2014a; 2014b; Ventosa *et al.*, 2014;
49 2015). These studies showed that in intermediate salinity ponds the dominant microbial
50 communities were members of the *Euryarchaeota* and a group of halophilic
51 *Gammaproteobacteria* phylogenetically related to the genera *Alkalilimnicola* and
52 *Arhodomonas*. A single strain, designated M19-40^T was isolated in pure culture from
53 Isla Cristina saltern (Huelva, Spain) and described as *Spiribacter salinus* (León *et al.*,
54 2014). This new genus and species, belonging to the family *Ectothiorhodospiraceae*,
55 was characterized by a peculiar cellular morphology, with cells staining Gram-negative,
56 non-motile and curved to spiral shaped. This species is moderately halophilic (growing
57 optimally at 15 % (w/v) NaCl and in a range of 10 to 25 % (w/v) NaCl. The major
58 cellular fatty acids were C_{18:1 ω6c}/C_{18:1 ω6c}, C_{16:0} and 3-OH C_{10:1}. The DNA G+C content
59 was 62.7 mol% (León *et al.*, 2014). The genome of *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T was
60 sequenced and assembled into a single contig (López-Pérez *et al.*, 2013), showing the
61 smallest genome described for any halophilic bacterium and also for any member of the
62 family *Ectothiorhodospiraceae* (1.7 Mbp). The genome is very streamlined with only
63 one rRNA operon and a median intergenic spacer of only 14-19 nucleotides. The
64 analysis of metagenomics datasets indicated that this bacterium was worldwide
65 widespread in intermediate salinity habitats and represented the first ecologically
66 defined moderate halophile (López-Pérez *et al.*, 2013; León *et al.*, 2014). Besides
67 *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T, another related strain, designated *Spiribacter* sp. UAH-
68 SP71^T was isolated from Santa Pola saltern (Alicante, Spain) and its complete genome
69 (1.9 Mbp) compared with that of *S. salinus* M19-40^T. The average nucleotide identity

70 (ANI) between these two strains was only 77.3 % (López-Pérez *et al.*, 2013), indicating
71 that they might represent two different species of the same genus (Konstantinidis &
72 Tiedje, 2005). In this paper we determined the exact taxonomic position of *Spiribacter*
73 sp. UAH-SP71^T by using a polyphasic approach, which included determination of the
74 phenotypic and genotypic features and a detailed phylogenetic analysis based on 16S
75 rRNA gene sequences. On the basis of these properties we propose the placement of this
76 strain as a new species, with the designation of *Spiribacter curvatus* sp. nov.

77 Strain UAH-SP71^T was obtained from a water sample of a pond of the “Bras del Port”
78 saltern, located in Santa Pola, Alicante, Spain (38°13' N 0°35' W) by direct plating on
79 R2A medium (Microkit) supplemented with 10 % sea salts (Rodriguez-Valera *et al.*,
80 1979). The pH was adjusted to 8.0 and the incubation temperature was 37 °C. The strain
81 was subsequently purified three times by plating on the same medium (López-Pérez *et al.*
82 *al.*, 2013). The strain was maintained at -80 °C in SM15 medium containing 50 % (v/v)
83 glycerol (León *et al.*, 2014).

84 The type strains *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T and *Arhodomonas aquaeolei* DSM 8974^T
85 were used as reference strains for comparative purposes. They were cultured under the
86 same conditions than strain UAH-SP71^T.

87 Cell morphology and motility were examined using an Olympus CX41 microscope
88 equipped with phase-contrast optics. Cellular morphology was examined as well by
89 scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (model DSM950; Zeiss electron microscope) after
90 growth on medium SM15 (León *et al.*, 2014) at 37 °C. SEM imaging was performed
91 with cells grown on inclined glass coverslips embedded into culture medium in a Petri
92 dish. Cells were fixed using 5 % (v/v) formaldehyde in 0.2 M cacodylate buffer, pH 7.2
93 for 1 h, followed by two washings with the same buffer. Cells were dehydrated by
94 washing four times with increasing gradients of ethyl alcohol ranging from 25 % to

95 100 % and twice with acetone for 10 min. The samples were stored overnight in
96 anhydrous acetone. Critical point-drying was then performed using liquid carbon
97 dioxide rinse cycles to remove traces of ethanol and acetone. Samples were heated to
98 30-40 °C to remove any remaining moisture. Samples were then sputter-coated with
99 gold-palladium. Cells were non-motile, curved rods (Supplementary Fig. S1, available
100 at IJSEM online). Colony morphology was observed on SM15 medium (León *et al.*,
101 2014) under optimal growth conditions after incubation at 37° C for 10 days. Colonies
102 were circular, entire, pink pigmented and approximately 0.2-0.5 mm in diameter.

103 Optimal conditions and range for growth were determined by growing the strains in
104 SM15 medium at 0.5, 3.0, 5, 7.5, 10, 12.5, 15, 20, 25 and 30 % (w/v) NaCl, and at
105 temperatures of 4, 15, 20, 28, 30, 37, 40 and 45 °C, respectively. The pH range was
106 tested in SM15 medium adjusted to the following pH values: 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 7.5, 8.0,
107 9.0, 10.0 and 10.5 with the addition of the appropriate buffering capacity to each
108 medium (Sánchez-Porro *et al.*, 2009). Strain UAH-SP71^T was able to grow at 5 to 20 %
109 (w/v) NaCl (with optimum at 10 % [w/v] NaCl), at pH 5 to 10 (optimum at pH 8) and at
110 5 to 40 °C (optimum at 37 °C). The strain was not able to grow in the absence of NaCl
111 and on the basis of the NaCl range and optimum growth under laboratory conditions it
112 was considered as a moderately halophilic bacterium. These values are in agreement
113 with the salinity range at which the strain was determined to be present in different
114 hypersaline habitats when its genome was compared with the metagenomic datasets
115 from hypersaline environments (López-Pérez *et al.*, 2013). All biochemical tests were
116 carried out at 10 % (w/v) NaCl and 37 °C, unless otherwise stated. Growth under
117 anaerobic conditions was determined by incubating strains in an anaerobic chamber in
118 SM15 medium. Catalase activity was determined by adding a 1 % (w/v) H₂O₂ solution
119 to colonies on SM15 medium. Oxidase test was performed using the Dry Slide Assay

120 (Difco). Hydrolysis of starch, gelatin, casein, Tween 80 and aesculin, production of
121 indole, nitrate and nitrite reduction, methyl red and Voges-Proskauer, urease and
122 phosphatase tests were determined as described by Cowan and Steel (1977) with the
123 addition of 10 % (w/v) NaCl to the medium and incubation at 37 °C (Quesada *et al.*,
124 1984; Ventosa *et al.*, 1982). Acid production from carbohydrates was performed using
125 phenol red base supplemented with 1 % of the carbohydrate and the medium
126 recommended by Ventosa *et al.* (1982). Urease was negative but phosphatase was
127 positive; nitrate and nitrite were not reduced; these and other features were confirmed by
128 searching the genes on the genome sequence of strain UAH-SP71^T; hydrolysis of starch,
129 gelatin, Tween 80 and aesculin were negative. The analysis of the complete genome
130 indicated that strain UAH-SP71^T and *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T are simplified in
131 their metabolic versatility, missing the chemolithotrophic and carbon fixation pathways,
132 and had very reduced ability to utilize organic compounds as sole carbon and energy
133 sources. Besides, predicted proteins related to xanthorhodopsin were deduced from its
134 genome (López-Pérez *et al.*, 2013). Other phenotypic features of strain UAH-SP71^T are
135 included on the species description and Table 1.

136 The 16S rRNA gene sequence (1,541 bp) of strain UAH-SP71^T was obtained from the
137 complete genome sequence (NCBI GenBank accession number CP005990). The
138 identification of the closest phylogenetic neighbours and calculation of pairwise 16S
139 rRNA gene sequence similarity were achieved using the EzTaxon-e tool (Kim *et al.*,
140 2012). The 16S rRNA gene sequence similarities between strain UAH-SP71^T and the
141 most closely related species *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T was 98.2 %. Other related
142 species were *Arhodomonas recens* RS91^T (95.5 % sequence similarity), *Arhodomonas*
143 *aquaeolei* ATCC 49307^T (95.4 %), *Alkalilimnicola ehrlichii* MLHE-1^T (94.9 %) and
144 *Alkalispirillum mobile* SL-1^T (94.5 %), all members of the family

145 *Ectothiorhodospiraceae*. The 16S rRNA gene sequence was aligned and checked
146 against both primary and secondary structures of the 16S rRNA molecule using the
147 alignment tool of the ARB software package. Phylogenetic trees were constructed using
148 three different methods, namely the maximum-likelihood (Felsenstein, 1981),
149 maximum-parsimony (Fitch, 1971) and neighbour-joining (Saitou & Nei, 1987)
150 algorithms integrated in the ARB software. The stability of the topology of the
151 phylogenetic trees was assessed using the bootstrap method with 1000 repetitions
152 (Felsenstein, 1985). The maximum-parsimony phylogenetic tree is presented in Fig. 1.
153 Similar tree topologies were obtained using other treeing methods: neighbour-joining
154 and maximum-likelihood (Fig. 1). The phylogenetic analysis showed that strain UAH-
155 SP71^T grouped with *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T and both strains could be considered
156 members of the same genus. This phylogenetic analysis based on the 16S rRNA gene
157 sequence is in agreement with the analysis carried out using a concatenate of 277
158 conserved proteins from the complete genomes of these two strains and other members
159 of the family *Ectothiorhodospiraceae* (López-Pérez *et al.*, 2013).

160 Genomic DNA from strain UAH-SP71^T was obtained using the method described by
161 Marmur (1961). The G+C content of the genomic DNA was determined from the
162 midpoint value (T_m) of the thermal denaturation profile (Marmur & Doty, 1962) by
163 using the equation of Owen & Hill (1979). The DNA G+C content of strain UAH-
164 SP71^T was estimated to be 60.4 mol%, a value closely related to that reported from the
165 genome (63.9 %) (López-Pérez *et al.*, 2013). The DNA G+C content of strain UAH-
166 SP71^T is close to that obtained for *Spiribacter salinus* (60.0 %) (León *et al.*, 2014).
167 DNA–DNA hybridization studies were performed by the competition procedure of the
168 membrane method (Johnson, 1994), described in detail by Arahal *et al.* (2001a, 2001b).
169 The hybridization temperature used was 54.6 °C, which is within the limit of validity

170 for the filter method (De Ley & Tijtgat, 1970), and the percentage of hybridization was
171 calculated according to Johnson (1994). The experiments were carried out in triplicate.
172 DNA–DNA hybridization between strain UAH-SP71^T and *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T
173 was 39 %, a level of DNA–DNA hybridization significantly lower than the 70 %
174 threshold value recommended for the delineation of new species (Stackebrandt &
175 Goebel, 1994; Stackebrandt *et al.*, 2002). This low DNA-DNA hybridization between
176 strain UAH-SP71^T and *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T is in agreement with the ANI value
177 (77.3 %) determined between the two strains (López-Pérez *et al.*, 2013) and clearly
178 supports the new species status for strain UAH-SP71^T.

179 The cellular fatty acid composition of strain UAH-SP71^T, *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T
180 and *Arhodomonas aquaeolei* DSM 8974^T was analysed by using cells grown on SM15
181 medium (León *et al.*, 2014) at 26 °C and at late-exponential growth phase. Cellular fatty
182 acid methyl esters were prepared and analysed by GC (6850 GC system; Agilent
183 Technologies) according to the instructions given for the Microbial Identification
184 System version 6.0 (Sasser, 1990) and were compared using the database TSBA6
185 (MIDI, 2008). These analyses were carried out at the CECT (Spanish Culture
186 Collection, Valencia, Spain). The cellular fatty acid profile of strain UAH-SP71^T is
187 given in Table 2. The predominant fatty acids were C_{18:1} ω6c and/or C_{18:1} ω7c (60.6 %),
188 C_{16:0} (9.3 %), C_{16:1} ω6c and/or C_{16:1} ω7c (8.6 %), C_{10:0} 3-OH (4.0 %) and C_{12:0} (3.5 %).
189 This fatty acid profile is very similar to that determined for *Spiribacter salinus* M19-
190 40^T. However, differences in the proportions of predominant fatty acids were found
191 between strain UAH-SP71^T and *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T with respect to
192 *Arhodomonas aquaeolei* DSM 8974^T; the percentage of C_{18:1} ω6c and/or C_{18:1} ω7c in
193 this later species is significantly lower than for the other two species (Table 2).

194 On the basis of the data from this polyphasic study and those previously reported on the
195 comparative genomic study, strain UAH-SP71^T is considered to represent a novel
196 species of the genus *Spiribacter*, for which the name *Spiribacter curvatus* sp. nov. is
197 proposed.

198

199 **Description of *Spiribacter curvatus* sp. nov.**

200 *Spiribacter curvatus* (cur.va'tus L. masc. part. adj. *curvatus*, bended, curved, referring
201 to the curved shape of the cell).

202 Cells are Gram-stain-negative, non-endospore forming, non-motile, curved rods 0.5 x
203 1.5 µm, occurring singly. Colonies on SM15 medium are circular, entire, pink
204 pigmented and approximately 0.2-0.5 mm in diameter after 10 days at 37 °C and pH 8.
205 Moderately halophilic. No growth occurs in media without NaCl. Growth occurs at 5 to
206 20 % (w/v) NaCl (optimum at 10 % [w/v] NaCl), at pH 5 to 10 (optimum at pH 8) and
207 at 5 to 40 °C (optimum at 37 °C). Strictly aerobic. Chemoorganotrophic. Catalase- and
208 oxidase positive. Hydrolysis of starch, gelatin, casein, Tween 80 and aesculin are
209 negative. Urease negative and phosphatase positive. Nitrate and nitrite reduction are
210 negative. Indole is not produced. Acid is not produced from D-glucose and other
211 carbohydrates. Methyl red and Voges-Proskauer tests are negative. The major fatty
212 acids are C_{18:1} ω6c and/or C_{18:1} ω7c, C_{16:0}, C_{16:1} ω6c and/or C_{16:1} ω7c, C_{10:0} 3-OH and
213 C_{12:0}.

214 The type strain is UAH-SP71^T (= CECT 8396^T = DSM 28542^T), isolated from brine of a
215 saltern in Santa Pola (Alicante, Spain). The DNA G+C content of the type strain is 63.9
216 % (genome data) or 60.4 mol% (T_m method). The complete genome sequence is
217 available under accession number CP005990.

218

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316

317 **Table 1.** Differential characteristics of *Spiribacter curvatus* sp. nov. UAH-SP71^T and
 318 the most closely related and the only species of the genus, *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T.
 319 Strains: 1, UAH-SP71^T; 2, *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T.
 320 +, Positive, -, negative.

Characteristic	1	2
Cell morphology	Thin curved rods, some short spiral cells	Thin curved rods, long spirals
Colony pigmentation	Pink	Dark pink
Cell size (µm)	0.5 x 1.5	0.3 x 0.8-1.8
NaCl range (% w/v)	5.0-20.0	10.0-25.0
NaCl optimum (% w/v)	10.0	15.0
Temperature range (°C)	5.0-40.0	15.0-40.0
pH range	5.0-10.0	6.0-9.0
pH optimum	8.0	7.5-8.0
Urease	-	+
Nitrate reduction	-	+ ^a
Phosphatase	+	-
DNA G+C content (%)	63.9	62.7

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322 ^a This test was reported as negative for this strain by León *et al.* (2014).

323

324 **Table 2.** Cellular fatty acid composition of strain UAH-SP71^T and the most closely
 325 related species. All data from this study unless otherwise indicated. Values are
 326 percentages of the total cellular fatty acids. Fatty acids that represented less than 1.0 %
 327 in all strains are not shown.

328 Strains: 1, strain UAH-SP71^T; 2, *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T (data from this study and
 329 from León *et al.*, 2014) and 3, *Arhodomonas aquaeolei* DSM 8974^T. -, Not detected or
 330 percentage < 1.0 %.

Fatty acid	1	2		3
		This study	León <i>et al.</i> (2014)	
C _{9:0}	0.6	-	-	1.2
C _{10:0}	0.6	0.8	1.2	0.4
C _{10:0} 3-OH	4.0	5.0	6.4	1.7
C _{12:0}	3.5	4.0	5.7	6.5
C _{12:0} 3-OH	1.3	0.6	1.2	3.5
C _{14:1} ω5c	0.8	0.5	-	1.2
Summed feature 2*	-	0.9	2.0	2.3
Summed feature 3*	8.6	7.3	3.6	16.0
C _{14:0}	0.8	0.7	0.8	1.7
C _{16:0}	9.3	8.8	13.4	19.6
Summed feature 8*	60.6	64.2	60.6	18.4
C _{17:0}	1.8	-	-	-
C _{17:0} cyclo	-	-	-	5.1
C _{17:1} ω8c	2.1	-	-	-
C _{17:1} ω6c	1.0	-	-	-
C _{18:0}	1.2	1.2	1.6	12.1
C _{18:1} ω7c 11-methyl	-	1.3	-	0.7
Summed feature 7*	1.9	1.3	0.6	-

Fatty acid	1	2		3
		This study	León <i>et al.</i> (2014)	
C _{19:0} cyclo $\omega 8c$	1.0	2.5	2.2	7.6

331

332 * Summed features are groups of two or three fatty acids that could not be separated by
 333 GC with the MIDI system. Summed feature 2 comprised C_{14:0} 3OH, iso-C_{16:1} and/or
 334 C_{12:0} aldehyde, summed feature 3 comprised C_{16:1} $\omega 6c$ and/or C_{16:1} $\omega 7c$, summed feature
 335 7 comprised C_{19:1} $\omega 6c$ and/or C_{19:0} cyclo $\omega 10c$ and summed feature 8 comprised C_{18:1}
 336 $\omega 6c$ and/or C_{18:1} $\omega 7c$.

337

338

339

340 **Figure legend**

341

342 Fig. 1. Maximum-parsimony phylogenetic tree based on nearly complete 16S rRNA
343 gene sequences showing the relationships between strain UAH-SP71^T, *Spiribacter*
344 *salinus* M19-40^T and other type strains of related genera. Filled circles indicate nodes
345 that were also recovered in neighbour-joining and maximum-likelihood trees based on
346 the same sequences. Numbers at nodes are levels of bootstrap support (percentages)
347 based on analyses of 1000 resampled datasets; only values >60 % are shown. The
348 sequence of *Thermus thermophilus* HB8^T was used as outgroup. Bar, 0.01 nucleotide
349 changes per position. The GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ accession number of each sequence
350 is shown in parenthesis.

Figure 1

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Supplementary Material

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Spiribacter curvatus sp. nov., a new moderately halophilic bacterium from Santa Pola saltern in Spain

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Suppl. Fig. S1. Scanning electron micrograph of cells of *Spiribacter curvatus* sp. nov. UAH-SP71^T. Bar, 2 μm.